

Research Article**A Quality Control Analysis for Improvement of Product Using Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA)**

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Abstract

This work presents a comparative study of the performance of the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) as well as the Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) control charts. The research is about quality improvement and systematic approach to reduction or elimination of waste, as well as rework and loose in production system. Starting from the data of a production process collected from the company, CUSUM and EWMA control charts were used to determine the (average run length (ARL) to detect a condition out-of-control. ARL found by each chart which was then compared. It was observed that the CUSUM control chart practically did not sign point's out-of-control for the levels of variation between ± 1.0 standard deviation. For these variation levels the EWMA control charts was more efficient than CUSUM. Among the variables the weighted parameter of EWMA control chart with constant $\lambda = 0.20$ with their respective control limits UCL = 532.43 of net content, 4.01 of gas volume and 11.81 of brix level were the ones that detected larger numbers of altered positions. The ARL results show that the EWMA chart is slightly superior to the CUSUM chart, when the process is out-of-control. However, when the process is in-control, the converse is true. Conclusively the Coca-Cola Company should invest more on research and development to establish whether it is possible for the organization to produce carbonated drinks that would have no side effects to the consumers.

Keywords: Chart, control, CUSUM, product

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Introduction

The Coca-Cola Company is the world's largest manufacturer, distributor, and marketer of non-alcoholic beverage concentrate (including carbonated soft drinks, syrups) and brands with headquarters located in all over the world. The company was originally founded in the United States in May 1886 when the curiosity of Atlanta pharmacist, Dr. John S. Pemberton, led him to create a distinctive tasting soft drink that could be sold at soda fountains. He created flavored syrup and took it to his neighborhood pharmacy, where it was mixed with carbonated water and deemed "excellent" by those who sampled it. Dr. Pemberton's partner and book keeper, Frank M. Robinson, is credited with naming the beverage "Coca-Cola" as well as designing the trademarked, distinct script, still used today. The first servings of Coca-Cola were sold for 5 cents per glass. During the first year, sales averaged a modest nine (9) servings per day in Atlanta. Today, daily servings of Coca-Cola beverages are estimated at 1.9 billion bottles globally. Annual report of the Coca-Cola (2009-2011) Prior to his death in 1888, just two years after the creating what was to become the number one selling sparkling beverage, Dr. Pemberton sold portions of his business to various parties, with the majority of the interest to Atlanta businessman Asa G. Candler. Under Mr. Candler's leadership, distribution of Coca-Cola expanded to soda fountains beyond Atlanta. In 1894, impressed by the growing demand for Coca-Cola and the desire to make the beverage portable, by Joseph Biedenharn installed bottling machinery in the rear of his Mississippi soda fountains, becoming the first to put Coca-Cola in bottles. Large scale bottling was made possible just five (5) years later, when in 1899 three enterprising businessmen in Chattanooga, Tennessee secured exclusive rights to bottle and sell Coca-Cola. The three entrepreneurs purchased the bottling rights from Asa Candler for just \$1. Benjamin Thomas, Joseph Whitehead and John Lupton developed what becomes the Coca-Cola worldwide bottling system. The bottling operation started in the Philippines as the company has grown; Coca-Cola is now sold in more than 200 countries, with consumers over 1.8 billion bottles serving every day.

The Coca-Cola company attaches more importance to the quality of their product as can be seen with the different adverts placed by the company; Quality tells the difference (in 1915), Coke adds life, have a coke and smile, it's the thing, where there is coke there is hospitality, the only thing like Coca-Cola is Coca-Cola itself, Coke is it! (1980) "Catch the wave" and enjoy the glass of a liquid laughter (2010). Many more till date is "Open happiness" in 2013, these are strategists of advertising the quality of their product and to meet up with the company requirement and consumers expectation in the market. The Nigeria Bottling Company Plc. (NBC) was incorporated in Nigeria in November 1957, as a private company, to operate for the bottling and distribution of soft drinks with its head-quarters and first plant located in Lagos and branches established in most cities

across the country. Its products include Coca-Cola, Fanta-orange, soda water, ginger ale, and Schweppes (Osaze, 1987).

Coca-Cola was an instant hit with Nigeria consumer and has reminded so. Over the next six (6) decades, Nigeria Bottling Company Plc. (NBC) has continued on its journey keeping its promise of refreshing consumers, strengthening its communities, enriching the work place and preserving the environment while recording many memorable milestones along the way. Over the years it has grown into business octopus and it is currently leading soft drink manufacturer not only in Nigeria, but in the West African sub-region. In Nigeria about nine (9) million bottles are sold per day with more than twenty (20) plants around the country that stands on their own for production. Maiduguri, "Borno State" plant is one of them which is chosen as a case study for this research. Nigeria bottling company Plc adopts both backward and forward integration in its expansion drive. Examples includes equality shareholding in Apapa Chemical Industries Ltd. (50.37%), Crown Products Ltd. (60%), Delta Glass Ltd, Ughelli (22.5%) and a plastic manufacturing outfit in Benin (100%).

Apapa Chemical Industries Limited produces carbon-dioxide used in all the Coca-Cola factories and excess sold to other bottlers; Crown products Ltd, Ijebu-ode produces all the bottle tops required by all the factories, Delta Glass Company, Ughelli produces bottles for Nigeria bottling plc. While the plastic manufacturing company, manufactures plastic creates for the firm (Osaze, 1987). The Nigerian Bottling Plc has over the years, and in lines with the indigenization policy of the Nigeria Government, sold shares to Nigerians. Its shares belong to the exclusive club of blue ships. Nigerian bottling plc controls to a large extent its distribution channels. It has Lorries that deliver its product directly to its distributors both wholesalers and retailers. It has kiosks, deep freezers and coolers painted in the popular Coca-Cola colors of red and white. These are given out to retailers on free lease but on the condition that no other brand of soft drinks is sold in them. Stores where Nigerian bottling plc products are sold are also painted in the firm's official colors at the company's expense. These measures have helped in no small measure to ensure an ever-increasing annual sales figure. The corporate objective of the company is to improve the share-holders' investment through increased sales and higher profits. The expansion programs of Nigeria bottling plc are geared towards exploiting the ever-increasing market demand for soft drinks in Nigeria (Osaze, 1987).

The Maiduguri plant of "Coca-cola" was officially organized and commissioned by Lt. Col. Abdulmumni Aminu the former governor of Borno State on the 25th of February, 1987 but actual production started in 1986 with the aim of meeting the high demand of the product in the north-east region of the country with initial staff strength of about 200.

Before the commissioning of the plant, the Maiduguri deport which was one of the biggest in the country was receiving supplies from Kano. The establishment of the plant in Maiduguri has led to the generation of employment opportunities for the local populace as well as increase revenue to the government for the past twenty-seven (27) years. The brands produced by the plant are; Coca-Cola, Coca-Cola light, Fanta, Fanta pineapple, Sprite, Schweppes, Still beverages, water etc. It is situated at pompom-mari industrial estate, off airport road. The installed capacity is twenty-two thousand creates (22000 creates) per twenty (20) hours working day. However, the plant has not been able to produce at 100% installed capacity due to problems associated with availability of raw materials, work stoppages as a result of machines breakdowns, lack of maintains and erratic power supply from the public mains (although the plant has a standby generator some time is lost in switching over and obtaining fuel to run the generator can sometimes also be a problem). But the plant is faced by insecurity and vandalization of electric power materials which really affects and hampered the production process.

The plant is divided into different departments, each with a departmental head and an overall plant manager. The departments accounts sections are headed by qualified accountant; the sales department, headed by sales manager; personnel department, headed by the personnel manager; the production department, headed by the production manager; quality control unit, headed by the quality control manager, workshop, headed by the shop manager; and the microbiologist. There is also an in-house dispensary manned by a staff nurse. These various departments employ highly qualified and competent staffs to discharge the duties for which the departments are set-up. To ensure accountability and up-to date record keeping the accounts department prepares monthly return which is submitted to the company's headquarters in Lagos at the end of every month. In addition, periodic auditing is carried out by internal and external auditors to ensure prudent management of funds. All requests for cash disbursements must be approved by the plant manager. The plant obtains most of its material needs from a central office at the firm's headquarters in Lagos, although there is provision for emergency purchases locally. The production line is highly automated, and it runs two shifts of ten hours each every day, however due to the security situation in the state, the shift time has been reduced. There is an engineer on duty twenty-four hours a day to avoid work stoppages due to break-downs. There is a standby electric generating plant to take care of the exigencies of power fluctuation. There are two (2) water boreholes to ensure constant and adequate water supply. The production machines at the first plant are currently been replaced by modern machine. The quality control unit and the microbiology laboratory are well equipped to screen both the raw materials and the finished good to ensure they are of the best quality. Substandard raw materials are rejected and any finished good that does not meet the set standard is discarded. To ensure

that the firm's products are made available to all desirable consumers, the sales department has a fleet of trucks that takes Nigeria bottling plc products to all the nook and crannies of the state on a round the clock basis.

The workshop is highly equipped and staffed with competent technicians and under takes routine maintenance and repairs of the firm's vehicles, equipment and machines. All repairs and maintenance are done in-house, thus a lot of savings are made since it is much cheaper than contracting the job to outside mechanics. Spare parts are supplied from the company's central stores in Lagos, although this practice sometimes causes delays, in exceptional cases local purchases are made. The personnel department is responsible for the recruitment and discipline of junior members of staff, and oversees the general welfare of all members of staff. Source: (NBC). The staff dispensary is manned by a staff Nurse and it is stocked with basic medicaments to handle minor ailments and to administer first aid in case of emergency until more appropriate medical treatment can be obtained. The plant also provides staff buses that convey workers from their homes to the plant and back home at the close of work despite fact that workers are paid transport allowance. Consequently, incidents of lateness due to transportation problems are rare. The company has a staff training school in Lagos where workers are trained periodically. Seminars and lectures are organized for senior members of staff occasionally aimed at improving the productivity of the workers and preparing them for higher responsibilities. Thus, it enables employee to update their knowledge and acquire new skills. The quality control unit of the plant is well equipped to ensure that products supplied to consumers are safe and of good quality. On the production line there are "SORTING POINT" which is brightly lit to detect "short filled" bottles and those that might contain foreign bodies. The plant has a reject limit of 1% that is, if more than 1% of any batch produced falls below the required standard in terms of quality and quantity, then it means that something is wrong with the machines and it is promptly investigated. The challenges faced by the Maiduguri plant is that, the insecurity affect them in the sense that people migrated from Borno State to other states which reduces the sales volume and also some of their technicians left, these really affected the production rate of the plant. Source: (NBC) Maiduguri plant. Conclusion: The activities listed here may not be exhaustive, but they represent those, the management of the plant disclosed to the writer. Besides, the extent to which the plant can involves itself in any activity is subject to control and direction by the firm's corporate headquarters.

Literature Review

Brief History of Quality Control and Improvement

Quality always has been an integral part of virtually all product and services. Frederick W. Taylor (1911) introduce some principles of scientific management as mass production

dividing work into task so that the product could be manufactured and assembled more easily. His work led to great improvement in production and the impact on the quality of production increase positively. Statistical method and their application in quality improvement have a long-time history since 1920 when Walter Shewhart of Bell laboratories, developed a quality control model that altered the production systems understanding of work. It enables quality control analysts to control the quality of output. The primary component of this model is monitor (control chart), which determines whether or not a stable system exists. No matter how well designed a process is, there will always be some variation from a standard level of performance. Consequently, it is logical to see the standard as a range. This is in line with work of Taguchi (1992).

Total quality control was developed in 1970s, by the Japanese. The name stands for a broad philosophy of quality, which is tied into the present day, highly developed theory of production Feigenbawm (1982). Notation developed by western electric and the Bill laboratory, the Japanese economic recovery plan, following the end of world war II, concentrated on high volume flow shop configurations. The plan was to obtain low costs with the best possible quality. The assistance of such masters of quality as Deming and Juran (1974) initiated this objective. Quality control as a function of reducing variance came naturally to the Japanese. The Japan productivity center acted as a clearinghouse. Great contributors to the theory included by Juran, Deming, Feigenbawm, Genichi and Ishikawa (1970-80's). Innovation of product qualities to improve competitiveness is a constant goal of the Japanese. A Japanese word, "DANTOTSU", means striving to be the "best of best". When we connect that word with "KAIZAN", which means always improving, we can understand the constancy of effort that is made to improve the products to the best competitor. The chemical industries were relatively slow until the late (1970s) and early (1980s), when many western companies discovered that their Japanese competitor had been using the designing experiments since the (1960s) for introducing new process and evaluation of new design of improved and reliable product, other aspect of product design including selection of component and system tolerance. This discovery makes statistical design experiment more important and result to extensive effort to introduce the methodology in engineering and development of organizations into industry, as well as in engineering curriculum. This American society for quality control was formed in (1946), it promotes quality control and improvement techniques for all types of product and services. It offers a number of conferences, technical publication and training programs in quality assurance.

Quality Control and Improvement

This is the set of activities that is done to ensure that product and services meets the requirement and are improved on daily basis, since variability is often a major source of

our poor quality. Statistical techniques which include CUSUM and EWMA control chart and design of experiments are the major tools use for quality control and improvement. Quality control is often done on the basis of project-by-project and involves terms led by personnel with special knowledge of statistical methods and experiment in applying them.

Management Aspect of Quality Improvement

Quality management ensures that an organization, product, or services is consistent. The effective management of quality involves successful execution of four main components; which are quality planning, quality control, quality assurance and quality improvement. Quality management is focused not only on product and services quality, but also on the means to achieve it. Quality management, therefore, uses quality assurance and control of processes as well as products to achieve more consistent quality. Statistical techniques include Cumulative sum (CUSUM) and Exponentially weighted moving average control charts (EWMA) and designed experiments, along with other problems solving tools are the techniques basis for quality control and improvement.

Variation in Quality Control

Variation is a normal feature of process characteristics for production processes; some variations are statistically random, while others are due to the actions of production workers. When the workers don't act consistently, they introduce non-random variations that reduce product quality. The key for using variation as a tool in total quality management (TQM) is to identify the random variations, which are natural to the process, and those due to worker inconsistency. TQM reduces the non-random variations by acting to reduce work inconsistency.

Reviews on CUSUM Chart.

The control chart is the widely applied technique for controlling the industrial processes. The pioneer work on Statistical Process Control (SPC) was done by Walter A. Shewhart in the earlier 1920's. Shewhart developed the basis for the control chart and the state of statistical control. Shewhart's chart are effective for detecting large changes in process parameters; however, Shewhart chart may take a long time to detect a small persistent shift in the process parameter. The ability to detect smaller parameter shifts can be improved by using a chart based on a statistic that corporate information from past samples in addition to current samples. One such chart is Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) control chart was first introduced by PAGE (1954) lead to a fewer researchers' attention in this area of quality control. The EWMA control chart first introduced by Robert (1959) is also a good alternative to the Shewhart control chart when we are interested in detecting a small shift. The performance of EWMA Control Chart is approximately equivalent to that of the cumulative sum Control Chart.

Page (1954) developed CUSUM charts in mathematical principles using gauging techniques, considering the importance of sampling techniques in the area of quality control. This chart plots the cumulative sums of deviations of the sample values of a quality characteristic from a target value against time. It is noted that Shewhart's control chart for mean is very effective if the magnitude of the shift is 1.5 -sigma or larger Montgomery (2001). Some authors namely Duncan (1974), Lucas (1976), Hawkins (1981), Lucas and Saccucci (1982a, 1990) stated that the CUSUM control chart is much more efficient than the usual \bar{x} control chart for detecting smaller variations in the average. Sparks (2000) suggested an adaptive CUSUM chart to detect a broader range of mean shifts. Arnold and Reynolds (2001) developed CUSUM chart statistics with the variable sample size (VSS) feature and with both variable sampling interval and variable sample size (VSSI) features. Jones *et al.* (2004) discussed the run length distribution of the CUSUM chart with estimated parameters and provided a method for approximating this distribution and moments. Luceno and Puig-Pey (2006) provided an algorithm to compute the in-control and out-of-control average run lengths and run-length probability distributions for one-sided CUSUM charts initialized using random intrinsic fast initial response (RIFIR) starting policy. The same RIFIR starting policy procedures for the two-sided CUSUM chart was applied by Luceno and Cofino (2006). Wu and Wang (2007) proposed a single CUSUM chart which uses a single observation in each sampling to detect mean and variance shifts. Several studies have been made on a comparison between the EWMA and CUSUM charts. Hunter (1986) commented that the differences between the Shewhart, CUSUM and EWMA charts have to do with the way each charting technique uses the data generated by the production process. Lucas and Saccucci (1990) compared the ARLs of the EWMA and CUSUM control schemes over a wide range of parameter values and found that the ARL of the former is slightly smaller than that of the latter. However, Woodall and Maragah (1990) noticed that the EWMA chart can be slower to react than the CUSUM chart, for some changes in the process. Srivastava and Wu (1993) studied the properties of the EWMA procedure under the continuous time model and compared it with the CUSUM and Shiriyayev-Roberts procedure. The results show that the EWMA procedure is less efficient than the other two procedures when the $ARL_0 \rightarrow \infty$. An interesting result, however, is that the EWMA procedure is less sensitive to the reference value when the shift amount is unknown. Reynolds and Stoumbos (2006) presented a comparative study on the performances of the CUSUM, as well as the EWMA charts. From the many comparative studies between the performances of the EWMA and CUSUM charts, the performances of both the charts are generally comparable. Since most of these studies are based on the ARL and MRL, the aim of this study is to determine which chart performs better, in terms of the ARL. CUSUM chart is a time-weighted control chart that displays the cumulative sums (CUMUM) of the deviations of each sample value from the target value. Because it is cumulative, even minor drifting in the

process mean will lead to steadily increasing or decreasing cumulative deviation values. Therefore, this chart is especially useful in detecting slow shifts away from the target value due to machine wear, calibration problems, and so on. If a trend develops upward or downward, it indicates that the process mean has shifted, and look for special causes. The plot points can be based either subgroups or individual observations. When data are in subgroups, the mean of all the observations in each subgroup is calculated. Cumulative sum (CUSUM) statistics are then calculated from these means. When you have individual observations CUSUM statistics are calculated from the individual observation. CUSUM charts plot the cumulative sum of the deviations between each data point (a sample average) and a reference value, K . Unlike other control charts, one studying a CUSUM chart will be concern with the slope of the plotted points and the center line. Critical limits for a CUSUM chart are fixed or parallel. And a mask in the shape of a V is usually laid over the chart with the origin over the last plotted point. Previous points covered by the mask indicate the process has shifted. The advantage of CUSUM is that each plotted point includes several observations, so one can use the central limit theorem to say that the average of the points (or the moving average in this case) is normally distributed and the control limits are clearly defined. CUSUM is used in any process where small shifts in the process mean faster than conventional control charts. (CUSUM) charts are generally used for detecting small shifts in the process mean. They will detect shifts of 0.5 sigma to 2 sigma in about half the time of Shewhart charts with the same sample size (Montgomery 1991). The point at which shifts occur is easy to detect by an inflection in the plotted points. They are, however, slower in detecting large shift in the process mean. In addition, typical run tests cannot be used because of the dependence of data points. CUSUM charts may also be preferred when the subgroups are of size $n = 1$. In this case, an alternative chart might be the individual X-chart, in which case would need to estimate the distribution of the process in order to define its expected boundaries with control limits. These statistical calculations involved are needed to make the method usable in practice, and they are as follows: First to make CUSUM line stable: As the numbers of measurements are taken, the probability that the CUSUM value may drift into extreme values increases. This is corrected by adjusting the CUSUM by an out of control criteria k , and resetting the CUSUM value whenever it crosses the target value. The consequence of this is that two sets CUSUM values are available they are;

- One-sided CUSUM chart: It creates an upper and lower CUSUM. The upper CUSUM detects the upward shifts in the level of the process and the lower CUSUM detects downward shifts. The one-sided CUSUM chart uses control limits (UCL and LCL) to determine when an out-of-control situation has occurred.

• Two-sided CUSUM chart: It uses a V-mask, instead of control limits, to determine when an out-of-control situation has occurred. The V-mask standardizes the deviations from the target value, and plots the deviations from this value and the V-mask detects both positive and negative deviation simultaneously. (Copy right@ 2015 Minitab Inc.). There are two (2) ways to represent a CUSUM, the tabular or algorithmic CUSUM and the V-mask CUSUM, of these two forms, the tabular CUSUM form of the CUSUM is practiced more. An excellent discussion of CUSUM control scheme is given by Hawkins and Olwell (1998). So, we consider the construction and use of the tabular CUSUM in this paper. CUSUM is therefore conceptually simple. CUSUM may be constructed for individual observations as well as rational subgroups. First the case of individual observations is considered.

Methodology

Computation of Control Limit

This chapter present the control charts derived from sequential probability ratio test (SPRT) of CUSUM and EWMA. Each of the control chart use control limits that change with number of subgroups taken from the process. The chart differs from each other in how they change as a function of the number of subgroups. The average run length (ARL) performance of the control charts are then compared with view to evaluating them. The bases for evaluating the control charts are:

EWMA control chart and
CUSUM control chart.

These are the two statistical charts that will be used to analyze the data to detect the samples that are either with-in-control or out-of-control control limits.

Sources of Data

The data collected for this research were documented, which is a secondary data collected from the quality control management unit of the Coca-Cola Company Maiduguri plant on 280 samples for the year 2014. The data used in this research were records of variables (gas volume, brix level, net content) during the production of 50cl bottles of Coke from the Nigeria Bottling Company (NBC) Maiduguri plant (Borno State).

The Cumulative Sum Control Chart

Page (1961) proposed the cumulative sum (CUSUM) control chart as an alternative to the Shewhart X chart. The CUSUM control chart is based on cumulative sums of the subgroup averages and is derived from the SPRT.

In a control chart application of the SPRT, one would continue to monitor the process until $\Lambda > A$ when the procedure signals that the process is out-of-control.

The SPRT leads to the following expression for detecting an increase in the mean of a normal process. The procedure would signal when

$$\Lambda_i = \exp \left[\left(\frac{\mu_1 - \mu_0}{\sigma^2} \right) \sum_{i=1}^t x_i + t \left(\frac{\mu_1^2 - \mu_0^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) \right] > A \quad (3.1)$$

This expression can be simplified by taking the natural logarithm of both sides of the inequality,

$$\left(\frac{\mu_1 - \mu_0}{\sigma^2} \right) \sum_{i=1}^t x_i + t \left(\frac{\mu_1^2 - \mu_0^2}{2\sigma^2} \right) > \log A$$

This decision rule can be algebraically reduced to

$$\sum_{i=1}^t x_i + t \left(\frac{\mu_1^2 - \mu_0^2}{2} \right) > A',$$

where

$$A' = \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{\mu_1 - \mu_0} \right) \log A$$

By allowing

$$\mu_1 = \mu_0 + \delta \sigma_{\bar{x}}$$

the procedure signals when

$$\sum_{i=1}^t x_i + t \left(\frac{\mu_0 + (\mu_0 + \delta)}{2} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^t (x_i - \mu_0 - \frac{\delta}{2}) > A'$$

Where δ is the standardized difference in the means under H_0 and H_1 . This decision rule can then be further simplified by using the cumulative statistic

$$C_i = \sum_{i=1}^t (Z_i - K), \quad (3.2)$$

Where

$$Z_i = \left(\frac{\bar{x}_i - \mu_0}{\delta_{\bar{x}}} \right), \text{ and } K = \frac{\delta}{2}.$$

The common choice of k is 0.5, which corresponds to a standardized magnitude of change in mean of $\delta = 1$. Thus, observations are examined sequentially until $C_i > A'$.

The CUSUM control chart sequentially compares the statistic C_i against a control limit A' until $C_i > A'$. Since one is not interested in concluding that the process is in-control, the cumulative statistic is

$$C_i^+ = \max [0, x_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+] \quad (3.3)$$

If this rule was not implemented the control chart would require more subgroups to signal if $C_i < 0$. The statistic C_i is compared to a constant h^+ . If $C_i > h^+$, then the control chart signals that an increase in the process mean has occurred.

For $\delta < 0$, the SPRT similarly leads to the CUSUM procedure for detecting a decrease in the mean of a normal process. In this case

$$C_i^- = \max [0, (\mu_0 - K) - x_i + C_{i-1}^-] \quad (3.4)$$

is compared to a constant h^- . If $C^- > h^-$ then the control chart signals that a decrease in the process mean has occurred.

To monitor for both increases and decreases in the mean, two one-sided control charts are employed. One chart is used for monitoring for increases in the mean of a process and the other is used for detecting decreases in mean. If the process remains in-control, C_i^\pm will fluctuate around zero. If there is an increase in the process mean, C_i^+ will tend to increase. Conversely, if there is a decrease in the process mean, then C_i^- will tend to increase. When $C_i^+ > h^+$ or $C^- > h^-$ the two one-sided CUSUM control chart scheme signals that the process is out-of-control.

Estimation of the process mean following the shift.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu_0 + K + \frac{C_i^+}{N^+}, \text{ if } C_i^+ > H \\ \mu_0 - K - \frac{C_i^-}{N^-}, \text{ if } C_i^- > H \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.5)$$

Recommendation for CUSUM Design

Some general recommendation for selecting H and K based on several research studies are given here. Define $H = h\sigma$ and $K = k\sigma$, where σ is the standard deviation of the sample variable used in forming CUSUM. Using $h = 4, 5$, $k = 1/2$, will provide a CUSUM that has good average run length (ARL) properties against a shift of about 1σ in the process mean.

One sided Siegmund (1985), approximation of ARL

$$ARL = \frac{e^{-2\Delta b} + 2\Delta b - 1}{2\Delta^2} \tag{3.6}$$

Where $\Delta = \delta^* - k$ for the upper one-sided Cusum C_i^+ , $\Delta = -\delta^* = -k$ for the lower one-sided Cusum C_i^- $b = h + 1.166$ and $\delta^* = \frac{(\mu_1 - \mu_0)}{\sigma}$ for $\Delta = 0$, use $ARL = b^2$. The quantity δ^* represents the shift in the mean, in the units of σ , for which ARL is to be calculated. If $\delta^* = 0$, we calculate ARL_0 and for $\delta^* \neq 0$, we calculate ARL1. The ARL for two sided CUSUM is

$$ARL = \left[\frac{1}{ARL^+} + \frac{1}{ARL^-} \right]^{-1} \tag{3.7}$$

Rational subgroups for $n > 1$, replace x_i by \bar{x}_i and σ by $\sigma_{\bar{x}} = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$.

The Exponentially Weighted Moving Average Control Chart

The exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) control chart was introduced by Roberts (1959) for monitoring changes in the mean of a process.

The EWMA associated with subgroup t is

$$Z_i = \lambda^* \cdot Y_i + (1 - \lambda) \cdot Z_{i-1} \tag{3.8}$$

Where $0 < \lambda \leq 1$ is the weight assigned to the current subgroup average and $Z_i = \mu_0$. Common values

Of λ are $0.1 \leq \lambda \leq 0.3$. The EWMA is sometimes referred to as geometric moving average since Z_i can equivalently be written as a moving average of the current and the past observations.

$$Z_i = \lambda \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} (1 - \lambda)^j x_{i-j} + (1 - \lambda)^i Z_0 \tag{3.9}$$

And the weights of the past observations decline exponentially as in a geometric series. Having observed a total of T subgroups, the statistic Z_i is plotted against the Control limits

$$L\sigma_{\bar{x}} \left[\left(\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda} \right) [1 - (1 - \lambda)^{2i}] \right], \quad \mu \pm \tag{3.10}$$

where L is a constant that scales the width of the control limits.

Lucas and Saccucci (1987, 1990) investigated the impact of different combinations of L and λ on the ARL performance of the EWMA control chart. The combinations that were investigated were chosen such that the in-control ARL for each chart was the same. They

found that EWMA charts with small values of λ perform well at detecting small changes in a process mean. Conversely, EWMA charts with large values of λ perform well at detecting large changes in a process mean. Hunter (1986) and Montgomery (1996) investigated the ARL performance of the EWMA chart and concluded that it is similar to the ARL performance of the CUSUM chart.

Design of a EWMA Control Chart

Several studies on EWMA suggest that

1. The values of λ in the interval $0.05 \leq \lambda \leq 0.25$ work well in practice. A good rule of thumb is to use smallest λ to detect smaller shift. Western Electric rule use $\lambda = 0.40$.
2. $L = 3$ (the usual three-sigma limits) works well. Average run length (ARL) for different combinations of λ and L are given in Table of Lucas and Saccucci (1990).

Rational Subgroups

The EWMA control chart is often used for the individual measurements.

However, if $n > 1$, replace x_i with \bar{x}_i $\sigma_{\bar{x}} = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$ in (3.11).

Results and Discussion

Data Analysis

The main focus of this chapter is the analysis of the data (number of samples of coke) obtained from the Coca-Cola Company Maiduguri for the research. The data used are records of the Gas measured in standard "Volume" of CO₂ at 32-degree Fahrenheit and atmospheric pressure where CO₂ Gas has a density of about 2.0 grams/liter, Brix (syrup) level is a measure of the mass ratio of dissolved sugar to water and is measured in hydrometer, and Net Content is measured in liters during production of 50cl bottles of Coke which are obtained from the Nigeria Bottling Company plc Maiduguri (Borno State) plant. The statistical chart that were considered using are CUSUM and EWMA control chart scheme. After computing the statistical analysis of (EWMA and CUSUM) control charts as presented in figures 4.1, to 4.6 respectively. The overall mean is approximately $\bar{X} = 476.27$, standard deviation from historical data is 52.17 for the Net Content, 3.5544, 0.47 for Gas Volume and 11.43, 1.12 for Brix Level and the subgroup of size (n) is 1. Minitab was used for the analysis and plotting of the charts so that one can see the general levels of the performance of the charts and effective of this control charts. **The average run length (ARL)** of a control chart is a common metric used to assess how quickly a control chart reacts to changes in a process. The ARL is also used when comparing the performance of two or more control charts. In this chapter, the ARL performances of those control charts were evaluated and compared.

The Overall Descriptive Statistics is Given in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics: Net Content of Coca-Cola

Variable	S/no	Mean	Median	TrMean	StDev	Se/Mean	Min	Max	Q1	Q3
Net cont.	280	476.27	496.80	481.97	52.17	3.12	341.90	510.10	494.80	498.58

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics: Gas Volume of Coca-Cola

Variable	S/no	Mean	Median	TrMean	StDev	Se/Mean	Min	Max	Q1	Q3
Gas volu.	280	3.5544	3.8300	3.5779	0.4734	0.0283	2.7100	3.9600	2.8700	3.8700

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics: Brix Level of Coca-Cola

Variable	S/no	Mean	Median	TrMean	StDev	Se/Mean	Min	Max	Q1	Q3
Brix level.	280	11.432	10.560	11.393	1.121	0.067	10.450	19.540	10.510	12.550

CUSUM Chart Method

The CUSUM statistic for Net Content was calculated using target value of $\mu_0 = 476.27$ as the mean, the subgroup size $n = 1$ the standard deviation is $\sigma = 52.17$, and the magnitude of the shift we are interested in detecting is $1.0\sigma = 1.0(52.17) = 52.17$. Therefore, the out of-control value of the process mean is $\mu_1 = 476.27 + 1 = 477.27$, reference value of $k = 0.5$ (because the shift size is 1.0 and $\sigma = 56.17$ and $H = 5$ decision value $H = 5\sigma = 5 \times 52.17 = 260.85$

$$C_i = \sum_{j=1}^i (x_j - \mu_0) + C_{i-1} \tag{4.1}$$

$$C_1 = (495.6 - 476.27) + 0 = 19.33$$

$$C_2 = (491.5 - 476.27) + 19.33 = 34.56$$

$$C_3 = (498.3 - 476.27) + 34.56 = 56.59$$

The Control Line is given by

$$\bar{X} = \frac{n_1x_1 + \dots + n_Nx_N}{n_1 + \dots + n_N} \tag{4.2}$$

The data were substituted in 4.1 to obtain $\bar{X} = 476.27$

To begin creating the CUSUM chart by calculating the upper and lower CUSUM control limit plot points using this equation:

$$\begin{aligned} C_i^+ &= \max [0, x_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+] \\ C_i^- &= \max [0, (\mu_0 - K) - x_i + C_{i-1}^-] \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

each plot point is the larger of either one of the two results;

1. Zero or
2. The sum of μ_0 and k, subtracted from the current subgroup data value, x_i , then added to the previous C_i^+ plot point (denoted by C_{i-1}^+).

Control Limits

Upper CUSUM Limits:

$$C_i^+ = \max [0, x_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+]$$

$$\max [0, 495.6 - (476.27 + 26.085) + 0]$$

$$= \max [0, - 6.755]$$

$$= 0.000$$

Lower CUSUM Limits:

$$C_i^- = \max [0, (\mu_0 - K) - x_i + C_{i-1}^-] =$$

$$= \max [0, (476.27 - 26.085) - 495.6 + 0]$$

$$= \max [0, - 45.415]$$

$$= - 45.415$$

$$C_i^+ = \max [0, x_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+]$$

$$= \max [0, 491.5 - (476.27 + 26.085) + 0.000]$$

$$= \max [0, - 10.855]$$

$$= 0.000$$

$$C_i^- = \max [0, (\mu_0 - K) - x_i + C_{i-1}^-]$$

$$= \max [0, (476.27 - 26.085) - 491.5 + (45.415)]$$

$$= \max [0, - 41.315 - 45.415]$$

$$= -86.73$$

$$C_i^+ = \max [0, x_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+]$$

$$\max [0, 498.3 - (476.27 + 26.085) + 0.000]$$

$$= \max [0, - 4.055]$$

$$= 0.000$$

$$C_i^- = \max [0, (\mu_0 - K) - x_i + C_{i-1}^-] =$$

$$= \max [0, (476.27 - 26.085) - 498.3 + 86.73]$$

$$= \max [0, -86.73 - 48.115]$$

$$= - 134.845.$$

Using the procedure, the control limits for net content obtained from the data in Table 1
 We have the following information.

$$\mu_0 = 476.27, \mu_1 = \mu_0 + \delta\sigma = 476.27 + 1 \times 1 = 477.27, K = \frac{1}{2},$$

Net content

Figure 1. Cumulative sum Control chart for Net Content.

The CUSUM statistic for Gas Volume was calculated using mean value of $\mu_0 = 3.5544$, the subgroup size $n = 1$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 0.47$, and the magnitude of the shift we are interested in detecting is $1.0 \sigma = 1.0(0.47) = 0.47$.

Therefore, the out of-control value of the process mean is;
 $\mu_{s1} = 3.5544 + 1 \times 0.47 = 4.0244$, reference value of $k = \frac{1}{2}$ (because the shift size is 1.0 and $\sigma = 0.47$ and $H = 5$ decision value $H = 5\sigma$).

Considering the data in Table 1. We have the following information
 $\mu_0 = 3.5544$, $\mu_1 = \mu_0 + \delta\sigma = 3.5544 + 1 \times 1 = 4.0244$, $K = \frac{1}{2}$, $H = 5 \times 0.47 = 2.35$
 gas volume

Figure 2. Cumulative sum Control chart for Gas Volume.

The CUSUM limits in Fig 2 show that both the upper side and the lower side are in control, we would conclude that the process is in control at all point.

Also, the CUSUM statistic for Brix Level was calculated using mean value $\mu_0 = 11.43$, the subgroup size $n = 1$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 1.12$, and the magnitude of the shift we are interested in detecting is $1.0 \sigma = 1.0(1.12) = 1.12$. Therefore, the out of-control value of the process mean is; $\mu_1 = 11.43 + 1 = 12.43$, reference value of $k = \frac{1}{2}$ (because the shift size is 1.0 and $\sigma = 1.12$ and $H = 5$ decision value $H = 5\sigma$).

Considering data in Table 1 of Appendix 1. We have the following information

$$\mu_0 = 11.43, \mu_1 = \mu_0 + \delta\sigma = 11.43 + 1 \times 1 = 12.43, K = \frac{1}{2}, H = 5 \times 1.12 = 5.6$$

Figure 3. Cumulative sum Control chart for Brix Level.

The CUSUM chart in Fig 3 shows that both the upper and lower limits CUSUM at period 81 is C_{81}^+ and C_{81}^- are out of control and back in control at period 120 is C_{120}^+ and C_{120}^- out-of-control at period 161 is C_{161}^+ and C_{161}^- , we would conclude that the process is in and out-of-control at different points.

Average Run Length Calculation ARL

$$ARL = \frac{e^{-2\Delta b} + 2\Delta b - 1}{2\Delta^2}$$

Where $\Delta = \delta^* - k$ for C_i^+ , $-\delta^* - k$ for C_i^- , $b = h + 1.166$ and $\delta^* = \frac{(\mu_1 - \mu_0)}{\sigma_0}$ for $\Delta = 0$, use $ARL = b^2$.

$$ARL = \left(\frac{1}{ARL^+} + \frac{1}{ARL^-} \right)^{-1}$$

For $K = 0.5$, $h = 5$, $\delta^* = 0$, then $\Delta = 0 - 0.5 = -0.5$ $b = 5 + 1.166 = 6.66$, we have

$$ARL_0^+ = \frac{e^{-2 \times (-\frac{1}{2}) \times 6.66} + 2 \times (-\frac{1}{2}) \times 6.66 - 1}{2 \times (-\frac{1}{2})^2} = 938.2$$

$$ARL_0^+ = ARL_0^-$$

Thus the in- control ARL for two sided CUSUM is

$$ARL = \left(\frac{1}{938} + \frac{1}{938} \right)^{-1} = \frac{938}{2} = 469.1$$

This is very close to the true ARL_0 , value of 465 shown in the table of Lucas and Crosier (1990). However, if mean shifts by 2σ , then $\delta^* = 2$, $\Delta = 1.5$ for the upper one-sided CUSUM, and $\delta^* = 2$, $\Delta = -2.5$ for the lower one-sided CUSUM. Then using equations above we have $ARL = 3.89$ close to the true ARL_0 , the exact value shown in the same table is 1.

Computation of EWMA Statistic Chart Method

The EWMA statistic for Net Content was calculated using the mean value of $\mu_0 = 476.27$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 52.17$, $\lambda = 0.20$ (weighted parameter) so as to come out with the appropriate value and $L = 3$. The EWMA limits for net content are calculated using the data of Table 1 and the control limits (obtained using Minitab) are shown in figure 4. The EWMA values are calculated as follows; The Statistic is

$$Z_i = \lambda x_i + (1 - \lambda) Z_0 \quad 0 \leq \lambda \leq 1 \quad 4.4$$

$$Z_1 = 0.2(495.6) + 0.8(476.27) = 480.14$$

$$Z_2 = 0.2(491.5) + 0.8(480.14) = 482.41$$

$$Z_3 = 0.2(498.3) + 0.8(482.41) = 485.59.$$

The EWMA values are calculated from the above procedure, for Net Content using the target value of $\mu_0 = 476.27$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 52.17$, $\lambda = 0.20$, and $L = 3$, Gas Volume target value of $\mu_0 = 3.5544$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 0.47$, $\lambda = 0.20$, and $L = 3$ and Brix Level value of $\mu_0 = 11.432$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 1.121$, $\lambda = 0.20$, and $L = 3$. The EWMA control limits for the three variables obtained from the data in Table 1 were summarized and the control limits (obtained using Minitab) are shown in Figure 4, 5, and 6 respectively.

The following shows how to set up EWMA-chart by the three-step procedure:

An in-control Run Length (RL) of 45. This is also the average run length (ARL) of the Westgard algorithm is selected.

Define the optimum shift to be detected as 1.0, and using this and the above ARL, gives a weighting factor λ of 0.20 with these selected value, the EWMA chart control limit (L) is 3.0 and for one control sample per day ($n = 1$), the central line, upper control limit (UCL) and lower control limit (LCL) are given as follows:

The Control Line is given by \bar{X}

$$\frac{n_1x_1 + \dots + n_Nx_N}{n_1 + \dots + n_N} \quad 4.5$$

The data were substituted in 4.1 to obtain $\bar{X} = 476.27$

Control Limits

$$UCL = \mu_0 + L\sigma_x \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{n(2-\lambda)}} = 476.27 + 3(56.17) \sqrt{\frac{0.2}{1(2-0.2)}} = 476.27 + 56.16 = 532.43 \quad LCL$$

$$= \mu_0 - L\sigma_x \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{n(2-\lambda)}} = 476.27 - 3(56.17) \sqrt{\frac{0.2}{1(2-0.2)}} = 476.27 - 56.16 = 420.10$$

Using the same procedure, the control limits calculation for Net Content, Gas Volume and Brix Level were obtained from the data in Table 3 are summarized in the following charts (Fig 4).

Figure 4. Exponentially weighted moving average Control Chart for Net Content.

The EWMA control limits of the Net Content of figure 4, the process shows out-of-control for the variable of weighted parameter $\lambda = 0.20$ and this indicate out-of-control signal between period 161- 200 and back in control at sample 201th - 280th.

The EWMA statistic for Gas Volume was calculated using the mean value of $\mu_0 = 3.5544$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 0.47$, $\lambda = 0.20$, and $L = 3$. The calculation for the EWMA control limits for Gas Volume obtained from the data in Table 1 are summarized and the control chart (obtained from Minitab) is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Exponentially Weighted Moving Average Control Chart for Gas Volume.

From the EWMA control limits of the Gas Volume of figure 5, shows that the process is in control from the beginning and out-of-control for the weighted parameter $\lambda = 0.20$

and this indicate out-of-control signal was at sample points 25th to 75th and back in control from sample 76th to 280th.

The EWMA statistic for Brix Level was calculated using the target value of $\mu_0 = 11.432$, the standard deviation is $\sigma = 1.121$, $\lambda = 0.20$, and $L = 3$. The EWMA control limits for Brix Level obtained from the data in Table 3 are summarized and the control chart obtained from Minitab is shown in figure 6.

Figure: 6. Exponentially Weighted Moving Average Control Chart For Brix Level.

EWMA control limits of the brix level of figure 6, the process shows that is with-in-control for the variable of weighted parameter $\lambda = 0.20$. The EWMA control chart has extensive application in time series analysis. The higher the weighted parameter, the faster it detects an out of control signal. Thus, providing validation of the methodology employed to set up Minitab in determining the weighted Parameter, limit L of the EWMA chart and the nominal ARL.

Discussion

EWMA was designed and applied using value of weighted parameters or smoothing constant (λ) which is 0.20. The values of control limits for the three variables used with the constant value of λ are calculated from the data in Table 1. The values of Zi (EWMA) were then plotted against the sample number for the constant λ and the corresponding

EWMA control charts are shown in Figs. 4, 5 and 6 respectively. It can be seen that, the charts for the Net Content and the Gas Volume shows that the process is out-of-control for the constant λ . For Net Content and Gas Volume, both charts detected the first out-of-control signal at samples 161ST to 200TH for Net Content and 25th-75th for gas volume, while for Brix Level shows that the process is in-control. CUSUM was also designed and applied using the reference value of $k = 0.5$ and $H = 5$, the control limits for the three variables used are also calculated from the data in Tables 1-3. The values of C^+ and C^- were then plotted against the sample number, for Net Content and Brix Level shows out-of-control also with lower control limit from 161st-280th for Net Content and at different point for Brix Level, and the corresponding CUSUM control charts are shown in figures 1, 2, and 3 respectively. Therefore, the larger the weight, the faster detection of out-of-control signal, while the smaller the weight, the slower the detection of out-of-control signal, hence the following comparisons are made.

The EWMA control chart gives an out-of-control signal at sample 161st-200th of Net Content observations (from figure 4) while the CUSUM control chart gives an out-of-control signal at 161 to 280 observations (from figure 1) with control limits of ± 260.85 . The EWMA control chart gives an out-of-control signal at 25th-75th of Gas Volume observations (from figure 5) while the CUSUM control chart gives with-in-control signal in all the observations (for figure 2) with control limits ± 2.35 .

For a one standard deviation shift in the process mean, the EWMA control chart gives an out-of-control signal on an average of 532.43, 4.01 and 11.81 of the three observations whereas the CUSUM control chart gives an out-of-control signal on an average of 477.27, 4.0244 and 12.43 for ($H = 5$, $k = 0.5$) of the three observations.

To illustrate EWMA and CUSUM control procedure Lucas and Saccucci (1990) have used the data of simulated observations from Lucas and Crosier (1982a). For normally distributed observations with an in control ARL = 500 and the parameters $L = 3$ and $\lambda = 0.20$ for EWMA, and the observations with an in-control ARL = 465 with reference value of $k = 0.5$, $H = 5$ for CUSUM; they have shown that the EWMA as well as the CUSUM control chart gives an out-of-control signal at the 161 observations (of Figures 1 and 4).

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summary

The quality control process of the Nigeria Bottling Company plc (Coca-Cola) Maiduguri plant in Borno State was studied in this research work. Measurements on three variables were taken and these are; the Gas Volume, the Brix Level and the Net Content. Secondary data on the production of the company was obtained with personal discussion with the

plant manager, quality control manager, the personnel manager and the production manager were used for the study. A statistic based on the quality improvement and its systematic approach or the “chart” of cumulative sum (CUSUM) and exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA) control charts were used for detection of product defectives and how to control them using the production process.

The challenges faced by the Maiduguri plant is that, the insecurity affect them in the sense that people migrated from Borno State to other states which reduces the sales volume and also the number technical staffs has drop in the company on quality control because most of the staffs has left, these really affected the bottling rate of the plant.

Also, when the ARL of the two charts were compared between the performance of ARL of EWMA and the performance of ARL of CUSUM, both ARL are similar in such way that one surpasses the other. The relationship between the Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) and Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) charts is that both charts were used for the detection of small shifts in the process of bottling in the company.

The findings will also help the company to know the problems of the quality control and their bottling activities and help them to identify the causes of loose so that effective control measures will be put in place.

The trend, the time of occurrence and the duration of the production process component are detected and qualified statistically. The time-average value of the production process within a time-interval is also obtained from CUSUM and EWMA control charts as moving-averages.

The criteria for detecting significant deviations from the bottling process level are expressed in terms of the standard deviation of the bottling process and inversely proportional to the value of the time-intervals used in the calculation of the CUSUM and EWMA control charts. The study is best summarized with regard to applications and assessment made from CUSUM and EWMA quality control charts.

Conclusion

From the results of the research, quality control can be seen as an ongoing inspection procedure, which is a powerful tool for controlling the production process. It does much more than just spotting and removing defecting items but also diagnose the problem of a process in delivering the specified qualities, and suggest corrective measures. This project has dealt greatly with inevitable need for statistical quality control in the production process of Coca-Cola company Maiduguri plant. In our applications and

analysis, the production of Coca-Cola found to be under statistical control, except that of CUSUM chart (for Net Content and Brix Level) were out of control while in the EWMA control chart (Net Content and Gas Volume) are out-of-control. In this study, the ARLs of the EWMA and CUSUM control charts are compared. The EWMA and CUSUM charts give different ARL performances under different situations. The EWMA chart surpasses the CUSUM chart when

$\delta = 1.0$, in terms of ARL1. However, when the process is in-control, the CUSUM chart outperforms the EWMA chart, as the ARL0s of the former are found to be lower than that of the latter.

The effectiveness of EWMA chart relative to determining shifts in underlying pattern and the efficiency of the charts relative to the time and expertise required to generate the chart was taken into consideration. EWMA and CUSUM chart were capable at detecting changes in the Coca-Cola production process (persistent) pattern when properly configured within Minitab. That is, it is very effective at detecting small change like mean shift of 1.0 sigma as used in this paper work. In view of our findings, we strongly observed that EWMA generally provided a slightly faster alarm than CUSUM since the EWMA methodology detects shift quickly for this type of dataset, it may be an efficient choice for monitoring it. Conclusively, the results indicate that the EWMA chart is slightly superior to the CUSUM chart, in terms of the ARL, when the process is out-of-control. However, when the process is in-control, the converse is true for such applications within this organization EWMA can be an efficient tool.

The conclusion of this study emphasizes that the Company needs to reduce its independence on carbonated and diversify its product portfolio into the non-carbonated sector to remain competitive.

Recommendation

A control chart is the graphic monitor of the production system. The user of the control chart is the process doctor. Like a doctor, he/she should be familiar with the process chart and the probable causes of certain pattern of variations. In the CUSUM and EWMA control charts, quality control methodology is essential to review and update the system's parameters so that decision can be based on "what is" and not "what was"? In respect of that the following recommendations are made.

The Brix standard should not go below or beyond the normal standard, these show that on the process of measuring the level of Brix (sugar syrup) and Gas Volume standard should not be increased or decreased with 0.01 from the measuring standard.

The Gas Volume should not be more or less, that will reduce the level of the defective production and it should be the specification of the customer.

The Net Content should not go below or beyond the normal standard; the content should be increased or decreased by 0.01 from the measured standard.

The management should address the constant break-down of machinery and tools to maintain continuous flow of production and activities as well as the avoidance of making profit for other NBC plants products transfer.

With the recognition that quality is an opportunity aspect of products, Coca-Cola Company Maiduguri plant should prepare to spread money to initiate and propagate a whole range of programmes to improve quality.

Quality control professionals (statisticians) should be employed in Coca-Cola Company to device programs that will enable defects and non-conformities to approach true zero (0).

The Company must have responsible, transparent and dedicated workers capable of mobilizing the entire workforce towards increased productivity.

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